

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE DOCUMENTARY-INFORMATION FLOW DEDICATED TO THE ETHNOGRAPHY OF WESTERN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of information resources on Western Azerbaijan ethnography, which is one of the important components of the system of socio-political sciences, and on the study of historical science, which is a branch of this science. The role of information resources is indispensable for the development and study of historical science. In this context, the analysis of primary information resources - especially books - is of particular importance. The study of primary information resources on Western Azerbaijan ethnography has observed its intensive development after independence. With the restoration of Azerbaijan's independence in 1991, the study of the flow of information on this region and its ethnography by researchers and investigators has accelerated even more. This article provides an analysis of a number of books on Western Azerbaijan ethnography. Along with primary sources, the article also devotes a wide space to the study of secondary information resources and electronic sources. The role of secondary sources, including modern electronic resources, in the collection and analysis of information on Western Azerbaijan ethnography has significantly increased. The idea that documents collected in various electronic platforms, databases and virtual archives allow for more complete and systematic research is also reflected here.

Keywords: ethnography of Western Azerbaijan, primary information sources, secondary information sources, document flow, information provision.

Introduction

Socio-political literature is closely related to the dynamic development of socio-political sciences, and this connection deepens with the formation of independent societies. Socio-political sciences, unlike exact and technical sciences, develop over time, taking into account the dynamics of society, modern problems and social innovations. This, in turn, also affects the content of socio-political literature. The transformation of society, the emergence of new ideologies and changes in the political environment play an important role in the creation of socio-political literature. For example, in recent years, the increase in the place of topics such as global problems, regional conflicts, environmental issues and human rights in literature reflects the changing demands of society. The development of socio-political literature also necessitates the reconstruction of socio-political bibliography. This requires not only the collection of new scientific resources, but also the systematic classification of modern research, scientific approaches and theories. Socio-political bibliography should become a system of scientific research that can respond to modern challenges by presenting new perspectives in accordance with the current problems, demands and needs of society [6, p.7].

Problem setting

The ethnography of Western Azerbaijan is an important field for understanding the cultural, social and political context of this region. Western Azerbaijan

is a historically and ethnically rich region, and various factors such as the cultures, customs, language and religion of the peoples living here have been shaped over time. Studying the history, culture and identification of ethnic groups living in the region requires ethnographic approaches, in addition to the methodologies of socio-political sciences. This means not only investigating ethnic identities and cultures, but also understanding how these identities are related to socio-political dynamics. Studies on the ethnography of Western Azerbaijan during the period of independence have the potential to shed light on the socio-political development of the region. For example, ethnographic studies allow us to better understand the dynamics of society by examining aspects such as conflicts, political changes and social renewal. At the same time, these studies reflect the unique cultural heritage of ethnic groups, their social structures and their contemporary problems. The study of Western Azerbaijan ethnography also influences the renewal of socio-political literature. Topics such as the renewal of society, ethnic composition, social justice and human rights are included in the research of socio-political sciences, creating conditions for a more in-depth study of specific issues of the region. In this context, it creates the basis for the emergence of new perspectives and broader scientific discussions on the history, culture and ethnography of Western Azerbaijan. It should be noted that in general, research in various directions has

been conducted in international journals [7;8;9;10;11;12;13].

The main part

Ibrahim Aliyev's work "The history and cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan", published in 2023, is an important scientific work dedicated to the in-depth study of the history and culture of Western Azerbaijan. This 99-page book presents a collection of studies aimed at restoring and preserving the cultural heritage of the region in its historical context. The main goal of the book is to clarify the historical heritage of the people living in the lands of Western Azerbaijan, its real situation, and to reveal the frauds carried out by the armenians. Based on extensive written and material sources, the author has examined the historical roots of armenian nationalism and the impact of this nationalism. The book prioritizes the purpose of the armenians and their supporters to manipulate historical truths and its consequences. At the same time, the work aims to combat the falsification of historical facts and cultural values, and to restore the true heritage of the people.

In this context, sections such as "The history of armenian migration to the territories of Azerbaijan" and "The armenian factor in Russian policy in the South Caucasus" present the historical dynamics of the region, ethnic relations, and cultural integration from an in-depth perspective. The book includes sections such as "Palaces and castles in Western Azerbaijan", "Muslim monuments in Western Azerbaijan" and "Christian monuments in Western Azerbaijan" covering various aspects of the region's cultural heritage. These sections also emphasize the importance of preserving historical monuments and allow readers to understand the rich cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan in a broader context. The topic "Caravanserai, bridge, residential houses and other historical architectural monuments" deepens the material cultural aspect of the cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan. The results of this study are a call not only to the academic environment, but also to the general public [1].

Thus, Ibrahim Aliyev's book "The History and Cultural Heritage of Western Azerbaijan" is not only an important resource for modern research, but also contributes to the understanding of the history and culture of Western Azerbaijan through a broader prism. This work not only acquaints readers with historical facts, but also provides an important platform for the restoration of historical justice and the preservation of cultural heritage.

The work "Western Azerbaijan", written by Humay Muradova in 2024, is a significant contribution to modern academic discussions in the field of ethnography, history and culture of this region. This 260-page monograph provides extensive and detailed information about the rich history, cultural heritage and social structures of Western Azerbaijan, which makes it a valuable source for independent research.

The introductory part of the work introduces readers to the historical fund of Western Azerbaijan. Here, the stages of the historical development of the region, ethnic diversity, socio-economic structures and

important events that played a role in the formation of culture are discussed in detail. The historical context provides a basis for understanding the unique characteristics of the region, focusing on the factors that influenced the formation of modern Western Azerbaijan. This section also discusses the strategic importance, geographical location and cultural ties of Western Azerbaijan. The other part of the book is devoted to the process of independent statehood of Western Azerbaijan and the return of national citizens. This part reflects the wide range of issues covered by political, economic and cultural transformations in the modern era. This part, which reflects the development of the region during the period of independence, presents the results of the latest research on the territory in a manner consistent with the requirements of modern society. It contains in-depth analyses of the challenges arising within the framework of the process of independent statehood, the political situation of ethnic groups in the region and their cultural identification.

H. Muradovan's work also aims to study in depth the rich cultural heritage, customs and traditions, nature, natural resources, carpet tradition, intellectuals and heroes of Western Azerbaijan. These aspects emphasize the historical depth and cultural diversity of the region. In particular, the carpet weaving tradition is not only an aesthetic value, but also a form of expression of socio-cultural society. The author analyzes the historical roots, development and place of this art form in the modern era, allowing readers to better understand the cultural richness of Western Azerbaijan. The last part of the book is devoted to the modern challenges and future prospects of Western Azerbaijan. Here, the impact of socio-political changes on culture, mutual relations between ethnic groups in the region and the preservation of cultural heritage are discussed.

The book contains extensive and accurate information on the ethnography of Western Azerbaijan under the headings "National-ethnic memory in Zangezur bayats", "Western Azerbaijan customs and traditions", "Western Azerbaijan nature", "Geological structure and minerals of Western Azerbaijan", "Western Azerbaijan climate", "Western Azerbaijan agriculture", "Western Azerbaijani carpet tradition", "Western Azerbaijani cuisine", etc. [5].

In general, the work "Western Azerbaijan" is a rich source for ethnographic research, as well as providing a broad understanding of the history, depth of culture and modern socio-economic situation of the region. This creates conditions for researchers, students and a wide audience in the academic environment to acquire deeper and more systematic knowledge about Western Azerbaijan. At the same time, this work draws attention to the important challenges for the preservation and development of the culture and historical heritage of Western Azerbaijan, thus providing an important platform for the transmission of cultural values to future generations.

In addition, there are many primary sources on Western Azerbaijan and its ethnography. As an example, we can cite valuable publications such as Aziz Alakbarli's "Monuments of Western Azerbaijan"

(2007, 272 p.), "Western Azerbaijan: in 10 volumes (Volume I 2000, 664 p. (and its updated form was reissued in 2003 with 736 p.), Volume II 2002, 736 p.), Ibrahim Bayramov's "Western Azerbaijan: Historical Truths or Armenia's Ethnic Cleansing Policy" (2012, 288 p.), "Historical Azerbaijani Land - Western Zangezur" (2023, 328 p.), Mirzali Farmanoglu's "Our Historical Monuments in Western Azerbaijan" (2010, 64 p.), etc.

It is becoming increasingly difficult to select documents and information consumers correctly and purposefully. This creates a need for better and more effective intermediaries. One of these tools is "bibliography". Bibliography is a field that plays an important role in the process of selecting and obtaining documents in modern information systems. It helps to use information effectively by creating a connection between documents and information consumers. The principles underlying bibliography and the specific features of this field allow for a deeper understanding of its functionality and impact. Bibliographic information exists and is used in society in various forms. There is a special form for the dissemination and effective use of this information in society, which is called "bibliographic material". "Bibliographic material" is an organized collection of bibliographic descriptions and notes. A bibliographic index, which is also a type of bibliographic material, has been developed for Western Azerbaijan, which is considered the first bibliographic material on this topic [2, p. 11; 22-23].

The work "Western Azerbaijan: Bibliographic Index" was prepared in 2023 by the Central Scientific Library of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences. The preparation of this bibliographic index is of critical importance in terms of systematization of scientific knowledge related to the history, culture and socio-social situation of the region. Also, this work acts as an important scientific tool in the context of the implementation of the Concept of Return to Western Azerbaijan approved by President Ilham Aliyev. The index covers research, monographs and scientific articles related to Western Azerbaijan, bringing together various scientific approaches in this field. This publication also provides an important reference source for future research. The bibliographic index offers the scientific community and researchers an important platform for further deepening existing knowledge about Western Azerbaijan and identifying new research directions. Thus, "Western Azerbaijan: Bibliographic Index" is a valuable resource not only for historical and cultural research, but also for the formation of modern scientific discourse.

The publication opens with the texts of the speeches of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev and President Ilham Aliyev on Western Azerbaijan. Speaking about this region, President Ilham Aliyev emphasized: *"Western Azerbaijan is our historical land, this is confirmed by many historical documents, historical maps, and our history. However, unfortunately, just like in Karabakh, the Armenians have razed and destroyed all our historical and religious monuments in Western Azerbaijan, and they*

wanted to erase the historical heritage of Azerbaijanis, but they could not achieve this. Because there is history, there are documents, and there are maps" [3].

An important place in the bibliographic index is occupied by the article "Scientific Chronicle of Western Azerbaijan" by the President of ANAS, Academician Isa Habibbeyli. This article deeply examines the scientific and practical aspects of President Ilham Aliyev's Concept of Return to Western Azerbaijan. Academician Isa Habibbeyli presents in detail the role and goals of ANAS in expanding and systematizing scientific research on this region of Azerbaijan. The article emphasizes the importance of the activities of the Coordinating Council for Western Azerbaijan Studies, and discusses the promotion of scientific cooperation, optimal use of resources, and the development of mutual relations with various scientific institutions.

A number of specialists played a significant role in the preparation of "Western Azerbaijan: Bibliographic Index". The scientific advisor of the index is the President of ANAS, Academician Isa Habibbeyli, and the scientific editor is Aziz Alakbarli, Doctor of Philosophy in Philology. The editing process was carried out under the leadership of Professor Mammad Aliyev, Doctor of Sciences in Philology. The compiler of the index is Khuraman Ismayilova, the chief bibliographer of the library. In addition, Sayyara Mammadova, Head of the Department of Innovative Projects and Methodological Support, and Shafag Aliyeva, an employee of the department, Doctor of Philosophy in Philology, supported this process as specialized editors. Such collective cooperation provides an important model in terms of systematization of scientific knowledge related to Western Azerbaijan and creating an open platform for broader discussions. As a result, this index provides valuable material for the use of researchers and the scientific community [15].

The bibliographic index consists of 9 sections that provide systematization of scientific information and cover separate areas. These sections are organized on the basis of the principle of classifying relevant information in chronological order and alphabetically. The structure of the index includes the following sections: "General section", "Religion", "Social and humanities", "Mathematics. Natural sciences", "Health. Technology. Agriculture", "Arts", "Linguistics. Linguistics. Philology" and "Geography. History". These sections cover books and articles published in Azerbaijani, Russian and other foreign languages, meeting the needs of researchers in various scientific fields. Also, "Dissertations or abstracts" is presented in alphabetical order as a separate section. Such a classification system allows users to easily access rich scientific knowledge in specific fields, which creates conditions for conducting research in a more systematic and structured manner. As a result, the bibliographic index makes a significant contribution to the advancement of scientific research and the increase of knowledge in various fields.

The materials presented within the framework of "Western Azerbaijan: Bibliographic Index" have a

structured classification covering the relevant areas. The “General Section” contains 253 materials, of which 58 are books (54 in Azerbaijani, 3 in Russian, 1 in other foreign languages), and 195 are articles (187 in Azerbaijani, 8 in Russian). The “Religion” section consists of 49 materials: it contains 12 books (8 in Azerbaijani, 3 in Russian, 1 in other foreign languages) and 37 articles (33 in Azerbaijani, 4 in Russian). The “Social Sciences and Humanities” section contains 515 materials, which includes 42 books (36 in Azerbaijani, 4 in Russian, 2 in other foreign languages) and 473 articles (357 in Azerbaijani, 116 in Russian). The “Mathematics. Natural Sciences” section contains only 10 materials; 7 of them are books in Russian and 3 are articles (2 in Azerbaijani, 1 in Russian). The section called “Health. Technology. Agriculture” contains 14 materials; 6 books (1 in Azerbaijani, 5 in Russian) and 8 articles (7 in Azerbaijani, 1 in Russian) are listed here. The “Arts” section contains 195 materials; 24 of them are books (16 in Azerbaijani, 4 in Russian, 4 in other

foreign languages) and 171 are articles (64 in Azerbaijani, 7 in Russian). The “Linguistics. Linguistics. Philology” section contains 745 materials; this includes 357 books (341 in Azerbaijani, 12 in Russian, 4 in other foreign languages) and 388 articles (376 in Azerbaijani, 12 in Russian). Finally, “Geography. There are 1709 materials in the “History” section, of which 492 are books (287 in Azerbaijani, 134 in Russian, 71 in other foreign languages) and 1217 are articles (1066 in Azerbaijani, 133 in Russian, 18 in other foreign languages) [3].

This systematic classification covers a wide range of scientific research and provides users with easy access to detailed and systematic information in various fields. The bibliographic index plays an important role in expanding and deepening scientific knowledge.

These calculations can be seen more precisely in Table 1 below.

Table 1.

NAMES OF SECTIONS	BOOKS			ARTICLES			TOTAL
	<i>In Azerbaijani</i>	<i>In Russian</i>	<i>In other foreign languages</i>	<i>In Azerbaijani</i>	<i>In Russian</i>	<i>In other foreign languages</i>	
General section	54	3	1	187	8		253
Religion	8	3	1	33	4		49
Social sciences and humanities	36	4	2	357	116		515
Mathematics. Natural sciences		7		2	1		10
Healthcare. Technology. Agriculture	1	5		7	1		14
Art	16	4	4	164	7		195
Linguistics. Philology	341	12	4	376	12		745
Geography. History	287	134	71	1066	133	18	1709

This table clearly shows the number of materials in different sections of the bibliographic index, the distribution of books and articles in different languages. This information provides a broad perspective on the organization of scientific research.

The section “Dissertations or abstracts” includes 116 materials, 105 of which are in Azerbaijani and 11 in Russian. It should also be noted that two auxiliary devices are used in the index: [3]

1. Alphabetical index of materials described by title (in Azerbaijani, Russian and other foreign languages);

2. Alphabetical index of authors (in Azerbaijani, Russian and other foreign languages).

Summing up the purpose of the index, it is important to emphasize its importance for research scholars, specialists and a wide audience. This resource provides detailed and systematic information about Western Azerbaijan, providing a broad framework for the history, culture, economy and other important aspects of this region. At the same time, the bibliographic index increases the opportunities for establishing connections between various research and

information sources, thereby deepening scientific discussions and promoting knowledge exchange. As a result, this index retains its importance as an important resource for enriching the research of the scientific community, supporting the development of scientific knowledge, and for future research.

When analyzing document-information resources on the ethnography of Western Azerbaijan, it is more appropriate to use electronic resources. The main ways to use electronic resources to increase the accessibility of document-information resources on the ethnography of Western Azerbaijan are: electronic libraries and databases, online archives, social media platforms, and cooperation between research institutions. These approaches ensure wider access to information on ethnographic research, facilitate the interactive presentation of resources with the help of modern technologies, and contribute to the preservation of cultural heritage.

Novelty

Electronic information resources related to Western Azerbaijan play an important role in conducting modern scientific research and studying

cultural heritage. The catalog of the M.F. Akhundov National Library of Azerbaijan, as one of the largest electronic catalogs in this field, covers various document materials related to Western Azerbaijan. This catalog provides a collection of not only books, but also articles, monographs and other scientific works, creating conditions for researchers and interested persons to obtain extensive information about the ethnography, history and culture of this region. When searching the electronic catalog under the

heading “Western Azerbaijan”, the obtained materials are classified according to several criteria. These criteria include criteria such as year of publication, bibliographic description, format, content, language, place of publication and location. In particular, the classification system based on the year of publication provides grouping of materials by decades. This approach allows researchers to easily find information related to specific periods and conduct their research more systematically [17].

Diagram 1.

According to their format, 418 books, 1115 articles, 17 isopublications, 5 notes, 4 book articles, 3 electronic resources, 2 maps and 1 periodical sample were identified among the electronic resources presented on Western Azerbaijan. This classification reflects how the resources are distributed in different formats, allowing researchers and users to more easily select materials that meet their specific needs [17].

At the same time, when books and articles are grouped separately by year of publication, the information obtained is presented in the following diagrams (diagram 2 and diagram 3). These diagrams help researchers understand how each format has

changed and developed over time. Grouping by year of publication makes it easier for researchers to systematically study literature related to specific periods, and at the same time visually demonstrates how the ethnographic and cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan has developed over time. Such a systematic classification increases the quality of scientific research and makes the process of obtaining information more effective. As a result, it provides a significant resource in the field of research into Western Azerbaijani ethnography, allowing for the application of modern scientific methods.

Diagram 2.

Diagram 3.

The “Western Azerbaijan. Electronic Library” project (<https://westernazerbaijan.preslib.az/>), presented by the Presidential Library of the Presidential Administration of the Republic of Azerbaijan, is an extensive electronic resource reflecting the rich historical and cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan. This project provides an invaluable source for researchers, students and the general public who want to explore the ethnographic, historical and cultural aspects of the region. The “Western Azerbaijan. Electronic Library” project brings together information in various formats - books, articles, photos and documentaries, etc., ensuring easy access to information for users. The goal of the project is to preserve and promote the cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan and support the development of scientific research [16].

The “E-library” section of the database “Western Azerbaijan. Electronic library” presents books and articles in various languages related to this field. This resource opens up wide opportunities for researchers, and at the same time serves to study the rich cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan.

When we classify the books by years, we obtain the results shown in Table 2 and Diagram 4 below. This classification allows users to easily find literature related to specific periods and visually demonstrates how resources have changed over time. Such systematic classification increases the quality of scientific research and makes the process of obtaining modern information more effective. As a result, the “Western Azerbaijan. Electronic Library” project provides an important resource in the study of cultural heritage.

Table 2.

Western Azerbaijan. Classification of books by years in the "Electronic library" database										
2024	2023	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	2017	2016	2015	2014
4	12	12	9	7	4	7	13	13	5	8
2013	2012	2011	2010	2009	2008	2007	2006	2005	2004	2003
7	12	15	21	15	16	12	14	11	11	11
2002	2001	2000	1999	1998	1997	1996	1995	1994	1993	1992
8	3	7	6	5	1	4	10	2	3	4
1990	1989	1988	1987	1972	1970	1969	1957	1956	1949	
7	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	

Diagram 4.

The “Western Azerbaijan. Electronic Library” project is of great importance in terms of preserving the rich historical and cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan with the help of modern technologies and presenting it to a wide audience. This initiative can be assessed as an important step in the context of preserving, promoting and transferring cultural heritage to future generations. Regular updating and development of the project increases the relevance and accuracy of the information provided, thereby strengthening its long-term impact. This approach has a positive impact on the systematic preservation and worldwide promotion of the cultural heritage of Western Azerbaijan. “Western Azerbaijan. Electronic Library” provides not only the systematic collection and presentation of information, but also the preservation of culture on a dynamic platform. This resource is an indispensable tool for researchers, students and the general public to study and evaluate cultural heritage. As a result, the presence of such electronic resources creates conditions for the enrichment of mutual exchange between cultures and ethnographic research. “Western Azerbaijan. Electronic Library” supports the sustainability and development of culture as a positive step towards modern scientific research and the preservation of cultural heritage.

The electronic library of the M.F. Akhundov National Library of Azerbaijan stands out as a resource that meets modern requirements by providing users with access to a wide range of information resources. Electronic databases facilitate the search for information for researchers and interested individuals by enabling fast, convenient and accurate access to information. This approach strengthens the library's activities aimed at preserving and disseminating cultural and scientific heritage, providing users with high-quality services.

One of such electronic databases is the database “Our Ancient Homeland – Western Azerbaijan” dedicated to Western Azerbaijan. This database contains rich information on the history, culture, ethnography and other relevant topics of the region [14]. Users can take advantage of this resource to learn more about the rich heritage of Western Azerbaijan. Such databases contribute to the deepening of scientific research, the systematic study and promotion of cultural heritage, and at the same time ensure its transmission to future generations. As a result, the database “Our Ancient Homeland - Western Azerbaijan” serves as an important resource aimed at preserving the cultural and historical heritage of this region.

Result

One of the most important documents of our time regarding Western Azerbaijan is the “Return Concept: A Concept on Ensuring the Safe and Dignity of the Azerbaijanis Expelled from the Territory of Present-Day Armenia, a Peaceful and Safe Return”. This concept, prepared by the Western Azerbaijan Community in 2023, aims to establish a general framework for the return of Azerbaijanis forcibly expelled from the territory of Armenia, and to ensure that this process is carried out in a manner based on the principles of international law, justice and peace. It also envisages necessary measures for ensuring the safety of the returnees, social and economic rehabilitation, recognition of their legal status and integration into society. This approach is not limited to resolving this specific issue, but also contributes to ensuring regional and international peace [4].

Recommendations

The increase in primary sources on Western Azerbaijan and its ethnography has significantly accelerated the development of research in this field in the last decade. The newly published books, which form the basis of these sources, not only provide

valuable research materials for historians, ethnographers and other specialists, but also open up rich analytical opportunities for a deeper study of the social, cultural and ethnic history of this region. The increase in primary sources on Western Azerbaijan, on the other hand, plays an important role in the creation of secondary information resources based on the analysis of these sources. For example, works of history and ethnography written in modern times systematize the information obtained from primary sources about Western Azerbaijan, transform it into a general concept, and present an analytical analysis of these works. Thus, works that serve the purpose of not only reading primary information directly, but also interpreting it correctly and objectively emerge. Thus, the existence of primary sources on Western Azerbaijan forms the basis of both historical and modern scientific research in this field. These sources are not satisfied with only collecting and describing facts about the past, but also reveal a deep analysis of historical processes and cultural developments and their significance in different periods.

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